

AxoloBot: Design and Development of a Bioinspired Robot Based on a Modular Platform

Daniel Arriaga-Ventura¹, Israel Ulises Cayetano-Jiménez¹, Rogelio Bustamante-Bello¹

¹ School of Engineering and Sciences, Tecnológico de Monterrey, Mexico City, Mexico

Email: a01338696@tec.mx, israel.cayetano@tec.mx, rbustama@tec.mx

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Abstract

This study presents AxoloBot, a modular robotic platform inspired by the axolotl (*Ambystoma mexicanum*), developed to support both research in multimodal locomotion and the practical teaching of control strategies in complex dynamic systems. The primary objective was to create an educational tool that effectively bridges theoretical instruction with hands-on experimentation. The development process began with a morphological and locomotor analysis of the axolotl, which guided the mechanical design of hybrid limbs integrating crank-rocker and wheg mechanisms to reproduce crawling and walking gaits observed in the biological model. The robot's components were modelled in CAD and fabricated using PLA-based 3D printing. A Proportional-Derivative controller was implemented on an ESP32 microcontroller to maintain a 180° phase offset between rear limbs, enabling stable and coordinated gait generation under typical use conditions. To assess its pedagogical potential, AxoloBot was integrated into an undergraduate control systems activity involving four students, who configured control parameters and analysed system behaviour in real time. Preliminary observations indicated improved comprehension of control principles and greater student engagement. A broader classroom deployment is planned to evaluate its long-term educational impact. AxoloBot represents a modular platform with potential applications in both robotics research and engineering education.

Keywords: Bioinspiration; Axolotl; Robotics; Multimodal locomotion; Research tool.

1 Introduction

Through evolution, living organisms have developed the ability to adapt by refining their physical characteristics, internal systems, and chemical structures to overcome environmental challenges. These adaptations serve as a repository of biological wisdom applicable across a wide range of disciplines (Primrose, 2020). Among these, the field of robotics has particularly benefited from biological inspiration, using natural organisms as models to design systems that replicate their key features. This approach contributes to enhanced performance, adaptability, and functionality in robotic platforms.

One example of this bioinspired approach is found in Central Pattern Generators (CPGs), which are small neural networks present in living organisms that generate rhythmic movements, such as walking, flying, or swimming, without direct supervision from the brain (Purves, 2018). These networks have been widely studied and implemented in robotics, enabling systems to produce several types of locomotion by modulating parameters such as frequency, amplitude, and phase shifts between signals. This capability provides more robust, efficient, and flexible solutions for robotic locomotion (Hogan & Sternad, 2007; Ijspeert, 2008). A notable application of this principle is found in the Salamandra Robotica II, a bioinspired platform that integrates CPGs to reproduce salamander-like gaits, showcasing effective transitions between swimming and walking in aquatic and terrestrial environments (Crespi, Karakasiliotis, Guignard, & Ijspeert, 2013).

Despite their versatility, CPGs present significant challenges due to their nonlinear dynamics and reliance on heuristic parameter tuning (Yu, Tan, Chen, & Zhang, 2014). To address these challenges, bioinspired robotic platforms can serve as educational tools for understanding CPGs, providing an experimental environment in

which complex robotic systems imitate biological locomotion. Through this approach, it is possible to gain insights into the behaviors and properties associated with different CPG architectures and parameter configurations. Additionally, these platforms support the teaching of control concepts such as variable selection, controller tuning, and performance assessment in real-world applications. By integrating CPGs with conventional control strategies, they help bridge the gap between theory and practice in STEM education (Kopman & Porfiri, 2011).

In response to this educational and scientific need, the present study proposes the development of a robotic platform inspired by the axolotl, an amphibian native to Mexico renowned for its regenerative capacity and neoteny (Gresens, 2004). Beyond its biological relevance, the axolotl exhibits functional characteristics of particular interest in robotics. Its locomotion combines spinal oscillations, tail propulsion, and limb coordination, enabling efficient swimming and supporting two underwater gaits, crawling and walking, making it a valuable model for studying multimodal locomotion. In addition to its scientific importance, the species is critically endangered, prompting conservation initiatives such as the program led by CONABIO in Xochimilco (Parrodi, 1999). Given this status, a robotic platform could facilitate low-intrusion ecological studies of its natural habitat, supporting conservation efforts and research on its exceptional regenerative abilities.

The proposed robotic platform fulfills two complementary purposes: it functions as an educational and experimental tool for the implementation and study of CPG-based control strategies in systems with six degrees of freedom, while also representing an initial step toward the development of a fully biomimetic robotic system that could support less intrusive in-situ biological research. This article begins by describing the biological basis of the project, including the morphological, structural, and locomotion characteristics of the axolotl. It then presents the mechanical design, with a focus on limb development, followed by a brief overview of the electronics and firmware. Finally, the results related to mechanical performance and locomotion are discussed, concluding with insights and future research directions.

2 Anatomy and Morphology

In order to accurately obtain the dimensions of the axolotl's body, we referred to a research study titled *Morphometric Description of the External and Internal Anatomy of Ambystoma mexicanum* (Ramírez-Macal, Chávez-Ríos, Velasco-Reyes, & Díaz, 2023). This study presents the average measurements collected from two male and three female specimens, as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Axolotl parameters and dimensions.

Assessed parameters	Average	Standard deviation
Weight [g]	31.6	6.88
Mandibular symphysis to tail tip length [cm]	15.70	1.96
Mandibular symphysis to cloaca length [cm]	8.30	0.97
Mandibular symphysis to cloaca length [cm]	1.72	0.27
Transverse length [cm]	2.36	0.21
Forelimb length [cm]	2.92	0.24
Hindlimb length [cm]	2.88	0.35

In addition to the anatomical measurements, the external morphology of the axolotl was examined to identify functional traits relevant to bioinspired design. This analysis, conducted through literature review and direct observation of a living specimen, aimed to extract features that could inform the robot's structure and locomotion.

One of the most distinctive elements is the presence of external gills, three branch-like structures on each side of the head, covered with filaments essential for gas exchange (Gresens, 2004). Another significant trait is its jelly-like skin, which improves surface adhesion, contributing to greater stability and maneuverability underwater. The skin also presents a variety of pigmentation patterns, such as black, mottled brown, white, and albino.

Additional features include four limbs ending in small fingers and a long tail with a dorsal fin-like extension. These elements allow different modes of aquatic locomotion, allowing the axolotl to swim, walk short distances underwater, and crawl along submerged surfaces.

3 Displacement Characteristics

In order to abstract the main elements of the axolotl's locomotion, observations and video recordings were conducted at the Axolotl Museum in Xochimilco, a centre dedicated to the species' conservation and research. The study employed non-intrusive methods, avoiding any physical handling of the specimens to preserve their natural behaviour. As a result, three distinct gaits were identified, crawling, walking, and swimming, along with their corresponding coordination patterns involving the limbs, tail, and spine. All these locomotion modes occur exclusively in aquatic environments, as axolotls are fully aquatic amphibians.

Based on the recorded observations, the first gait analysed was crawling, in which the axolotl moves on its belly, with diagonal limbs moving in a symmetrical swaying pattern, while the spine and tail oscillate with an approximate 180° phase offset. This gait closely resembles the crawling pattern of *Pleurodeles waltl*, which served as a reference for the design of the Pleurobot (Karakasiliotis, et al., 2016). Walking shares the same coordination pattern as crawling, but with a greater range of motion in the limbs, which support most of the body weight due to buoyancy, allowing a lifted posture and more controlled steps. In swimming, the limbs remain close to the body to reduce drag, and propulsion is produced by a propagating wave motion of the spine and tail, similar to the swimming behaviour of *Pleurodeles waltl* (Karakasiliotis, et al., 2016).

4 Mechanical Design

The mechanical design of AxoloBot is inspired on the anatomical elements and locomotion patterns of the axolotl. The development process included several iterations using CAD modelling and 3D printing. The robot is composed of modular parts such as limbs, spine, tail, head, and a central body, each designed to perform specific functions while maintaining ease of assembly. Particular attention was given to replicating crawling and walking movements through the integration of mechanical linkages and adaptable components.

4.1 Limbs design

This study focuses on replicating two of the axolotl's three locomotion modes, crawling and walking, using a single mechanical system. To achieve this, two complementary mechanisms were selected based on their kinematic characteristics: a crank rocker mechanism for crawling and a whleg mechanism for walking. These mechanisms were integrated into a unified limb structure capable of switching between gaits. The design process was iterative, with progressive refinements made to improve geometry and functionality. A key element enabling this versatility is a mechanical switching system that employs an L-shaped shaft, mounted on the

second largest link. This shaft allows the link to be detached from the fixed bar and reattached to the smallest link, enabling the mechanism to transition from crank rocker to wheg configuration. This design allows for the reconfiguration of locomotion modes with minimal alterations to the mechanical structure.

In the crawling configuration depicted in Figure 1, the crank rocker mechanism generates a partial circular trajectory that mimics the contact motion observed in biological crawling. The path resembles a crescent moon, enabling the limb to apply forward force at the lowest point while avoiding surface contact at the highest. This movement is suited for low-amplitude, near-ground propulsion.

In the walking mode shown in Figure 2, the wheg mechanism produces a larger, circular trajectory with symmetrical movement of 40 mm along both the X and Y axes. This increased amplitude allows the robot to clear small underwater obstacles more effectively. Notably, forward motion in this configuration requires the motor to rotate in the opposite direction compared to the crawling mode.

Figure 1. Simulated crawling trajectory of the limb driven by a crank-rocker mechanism.

Figure 2. Simulated walking trajectory of the limb driven by a wheg mechanism.

The final prototype was manufactured using PLA for the structural components via 3D printing. 1 mm steel axles and 1 mm metal bearings were used to enhance rotational movement at the joints. Additionally, the largest link in each limb was fitted with a rubber cover designed to imitate the axolotl's skin texture, improving grip and stability during contact with submerged surfaces.

4.2 Central Body Module

The central body module serves as the structural and functional core of AxoloBot. It supports the attachment of two limbs, one on each side, houses the main PCB, and provides alignment for the drive system. The design integrates mounts for Pololu gearmotors, structural supports for limb suspension, and double helical gears that transmit power from the motor to the limbs with a 2:1 reduction ratio. Its configuration ensures modular connectivity and compact integration of mechanical and electronic components. The module was 3D printed using UV-sensitive resin.

4.3 Modular Mechanism

To promote simplicity and reusability, a modular bevel gear system was designed for the head, spine, and tail. The gear train uses a 1.5:1 reduction ratio to increase torque while maintaining a compact layout. The mechanism includes a Pololu™ ball caster to support crawling motion, along with opposing bearings that guide a cable-based push-pull system. This configuration enables directional locomotion through continuous motor rotation, eliminating the need for motor reversal and simplifying actuation.

4.4 Limb Suspension

A dual-spring suspension system was implemented to maintain ground contact and improve adaptability to uneven terrain. The mechanism consists of two springs mounted around a rotating axle that holds the motor housings, one stronger spring positioned below and a weaker one above. This configuration allows the axle, and consequently the legs, to rotate slightly in response to surface variations. As a result, the legs can adjust their angle of attack passively, improving terrain adaptability while maintaining stability and continuous contact with the ground.

4.5 Tail

The tail is actuated via two side-attached cables connected to the modular mechanism. The system operates through a push-pull configuration, enabling undulatory motion by alternately pulling and pushing each side of the tail. The tail itself is made of Shore 20A silicone rubber, providing the flexibility needed for smooth deformation. Its structure includes interlocking base protrusions for alignment and lateral cutouts to reduce weight while maintaining structural integrity.

4.6 Spine

The spine consists of three compliant elements made of Shore 20A silicone rubber that connect the central modules in sequence. The central piece, smaller in size, is anchored to two modular mechanisms: one containing the bevel gear system that drives cable-based push-pull actuation for generating undulatory motion, and the other providing structural support. The two lateral elements connect to the sides of the modules, reinforcing the overall structure and contributing to the visual coherence of the design.

4.7 Head

The design of the head was conceived with the primary objective of integrating sensors to capture essential environmental data and facilitate communication with the various microcontrollers distributed throughout the body. To this end, a designated cavity was crafted within the head, paired with a shaft to house a gear from the modular mechanism, thus enabling the capability for movement. However, due to time constraints, our implementation efforts were limited to the structural model of the head and the installation of the gear.

4.8 Final Design

The final design of AxoloBot, depicted in Figure 3, integrates features inspired by the anatomy and locomotion of the axolotl. The robot is modular, allowing for easy disassembly and rapid replacement of components. Its limbs can switch between crawling and walking modes through a reconfigurable mechanism. The suspension system provides terrain adaptability, while the compliant silicone tail and articulated spine enhance movement fluidity. The central module houses the electronics and supports all actuators, enabling compact integration.

Figure 3. AxoloBot final design

5 Electronics

The electronic system is centred around a custom PCB designed by co-author Israel Cayetano, responsible for motor control and communication. The board integrates an ESP32-PICO microcontroller, DRV8231A motor drivers, a 6 V power input, and JST-SH connectors for UART, I²C, and motor/encoder interfaces. The PCB distributes power, generates PWM control signals, and reads feedback from motor encoders.

The actuation system employs Pololu 6V Micro-Metal Gearmotors (150.58:1 reduction), offering 2 kg·cm stall torque and compact dimensions (10×12 mm). Each motor is paired with a Pololu magnetic quadrature encoder, providing 12 counts per revolution and operating within a 2.7–18 V range. The six-pin JST-SH connector enables power, signal, and motor connection in a compact layout.

6 Firmware

The control architecture was designed to ensure coordinated locomotion by maintaining consistent phase offsets between the limbs, spine, and tail. To this end, an initial evaluation of the control variable was conducted, comparing speed and position. Speed control, which relies on maintaining continuous motor rotation, was found to be prone to phase offset loss when external disturbances or obstacles are present. As a result, angular position was selected as the control variable, since it continuously seeks to reach the reference position, preserving coordination even under perturbations.

Based on this decision, the firmware was developed to implement angular position control through a Proportional-Derivative (PD) controller. The control process begins with the generation of reference signals by oscillators, which define the target angular positions for each joint. These references are compared with the measured positions obtained from quadrature encoders to calculate the control error. The error is then processed by the PD controller, whose output determines the corresponding PWM signal. This signal is applied to the motors through an H-bridge to execute the desired motion. This control logic was implemented using

an object-oriented programming approach, resulting in a modular firmware architecture. The following list outlines the libraries used in its implementation.

- Oscillator: Generates reference positions and provides the 180° phase shift.
- Encoder: Captures angular position using quadrature signals.
- PWM: Regulates the motor's power via duty cycle control.
- Controller: Implements PD control to compute the appropriate duty cycle.
- H-Bridge: Sets motor direction and applies PWM input.
- Servo: Integrates the above libraries to simplify limb control.

7 Results and Discussion

Figure 4 compares the dimensions of a mature male axolotl and the AxoloBot. The robot's body length is scaled 1.5 times, the tail is 0.77 times shorter, and limb spacing is increased by a factor of 3.07. These disproportions result from constraints such as motor size and component layout. While functional, they indicate the need for future morphological adjustments to enhance fidelity and enable less intrusive field deployment.

In addition to morphological assessment, structural performance was evaluated through static simulation using Von Mises stress analysis. The simulation considered a load equivalent to half the robot's total mass (410g), representing a typical scenario in which one limb supports the body during stance. All critical components remained well below the PLA yield range (55–72 MPa). The limb, which bears the entire support load during propulsion, exhibited the highest stress level, reaching a maximum of 2.92 MPa. These results confirm that the robot's mechanical structure can safely support its own weight and endure routine mechanical impacts.

Moreover, the control system was evaluated by analysing the angular response of the rear limb motors in crawling mode (Figure 5). The results confirm that the system maintains the required 180° phase offset between the limbs, ensuring proper gait coordination. However, Motor 1 showed slower convergence and a noticeable overshoot around 4000 ms, caused by internal friction or a brief mechanical obstruction. Initial delays and overshoot were observed, due to static friction and mechanical tolerances, suggesting areas for future refinement.

In summary, the control system achieves stable phase coordination with minimal deviation from reference trajectories, validating the robot's design. While improvements in mechanical tolerance and adaptability are planned, AxoloBot has already been used in a hands-on activity with four undergraduate students. During this activity, they selected control variables and tuned PD parameters, reinforcing their understanding of locomotion control through direct experimentation. A classroom trial is planned to further assess its educational effectiveness in teaching system dynamics and robotic coordination.

Figure 4. Mexican axolotl and Axolobot dimensions comparison

Figure 5. (A) Motors' angular position versus reference. (B) Robot configuration showing motor locations during crawling.

8 Conclusion

This work presented the development of a bioinspired robotic platform modelled after the axolotl, with emphasis on structural design, proportion analysis, and low-level control strategies. Finite element simulations confirmed that the mechanical structure remains within safe stress limits under expected loading conditions, validating its suitability for experimental use.

Although the current prototype achieves functional locomotion, discrepancies in body proportions relative to a mature axolotl limit its morphological fidelity. Additionally, the current model requires manual intervention to switch between locomotion modes. A future redesign will address these limitations by refining limb geometry, improving surface contact to reduce slippage, implementing an automatic mode-switching mechanism, and redistributing the electronic components to achieve body proportions more closely aligned with those of the real specimen.

In parallel, the control system was tested in a design activity involving four undergraduate students, who tuned PD parameters and observed coordination behaviour. This experience demonstrated AxoloBot's value as an educational platform for robotics and control. A classroom trial is under development to evaluate its impact on student understanding of hybrid locomotion and system dynamics.

Moreover, experimental results demonstrated the robot's capacity to perform two coordinated gaits with acceptable position tracking. Nevertheless, to improve robustness against disturbances, the integration of CPGs is proposed. In particular, Matsuoka-based CPGs with sensory feedback, as explored in prior studies (Fukuoka, Kimura, & Cohen, 2003), offer a promising approach to enhance adaptability and gait stability in dynamic environments.

Future efforts will focus on parameterizing the CPG model based on empirical data from axolotl locomotion, considering gait amplitude, frequency, and inter-limb phase offset, and on exploring neural modulation for adaptive gait control (Harris-Warrick, 2011). Additional developments include sensor integration for environmental data acquisition and autonomous navigation, inspired by aquatic platforms such as AQUA (Dudek, y otros, 2007). Waterproofing solutions will be explored to enable full underwater operation, including the implementation of a Dragon Skin silicone suit, selected for its flexibility, durability, and resemblance to the texture of axolotl's skin.

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